

Supplementary Information:

Decomposition of benzene during impacts in N₂-dominated atmospheres

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1 Benzene decomposition and fits

Shown below are figures with benzene decomposition in the experiment and their respective fits. Both the data generation process and fitting are described in the main text.

Figure S1: Experiment no. 1 as labeled in Table 1 in the main text and the respective fit.

Figure S2: Experiment no. 2 as labeled in Table 1 in the main text and the respective fit.

Figure S3: Experiment no. 3 as labeled in Table 1 in the main text and the respective fit.

Figure S4: Experiment no. 4 as labeled in Table 1 in the main text and the respective fit.

Figure S5: Experiment no. 5 as labeled in Table 1 in the main text and the respective fit.

Figure S6: Experiment no. 6 as labeled in Table 1 in the main text and the respective fit.

Figure S7: Experiment no. 8 as labeled in Table 1 in the main text and the respective fit.

Figure S8: Experiment no. 9 as labeled in Table 1 in the main text and the respective fit.

2 Fitted rate constants

Table S1: Fitted rate constants for benzene decomposition according to eq. 2 in the main text.

Experiment	k_1' [Torr s ⁻¹]	k_1' (fit uncertainty) [Torr s ⁻¹]	k_2' [Torr]	k_2' (fit uncertainty) [Torr]
1	8.19E-03	6.60E-03	6.64	6.79
2	7.93E-03	3.61E-04	5.68	3.84E-01
3	9.81E-03	7.27E-03	8.33	7.83
4	1.25E-02	3.65E-03	9.89	3.64
5	1.79E-02	9.47E-03	1.19E+01	7.93
6	3.43E-03	8.40E-04	9.87E-01	4.03E-01
7	1.35E-03	1.06E-04	1.95E-01	4.08E-02
8	6.89E-03	2.29E-03	1.81	8.85E-01
9	7.45E-03	1.85E-03	2.75	9.75E-01

3 Complete mixture compositions

Table S2: Initial and final compositions of all samples in the experiment.

Experiment	State	Total energy (J)	Time (s)	P (C ₂ H ₂ , Torr)	P (HCN, Torr)	P (benzene, Torr)	P (H ₂ O, Torr)	P (CO ₂ , Torr)	P (CO, Torr)	P (CH ₄ , Torr)
1	initial	0	0	0	0	2.656 ± 0.002	0.191 ± 0.002	0.00021 ± 0.00003	0.000	0.000
1	final	7650	1700	0.769 ± 0.003	1.771 ± 0.005	0.552 ± 0.005	0.164 ± 0.002	0.00256 ± 0.00005	0.3903 ± 0.0005	0.081 ± 0.009
2	initial	0	0	0	0.0073 ± 0.002	2.866 ± 0.005	0.466 ± 0.003	0.00030 ± 0.00003	0.0002 ± 0.0001	0.001 ± 0.005
2	final	7650	1700	0.828 ± 0.004	2.064 ± 0.006	0.396 ± 0.006	0.319 ± 0.002	0.00253 ± 0.00005	0.514 ± 0.001	0.09 ± 0.01
3	initial	0	0	0.0015 ± 0.0009	0.009 ± 0.002	3.33 ± 0.02	2.61 ± 0.01	0.00081 ± 0.00004	0.0007 ± 0.0004	0.000
3	final	7650	1700	1.165 ± 0.004	2.063 ± 0.006	0.74 ± 0.02	1.457 ± 0.007	0.00912 ± 0.00006	1.742 0.002	0.13 ± 0.01
4	initial	0	0	0	0.009 ± 0.002	3.95 ± 0.05	7.12 ± 0.03	0.00091 ± 0.00004	0.00005 0.00024	0.00
4	final	7650	1700	0.930 ± 0.004	2.086 ± 0.006	0.69 ± 0.03	3.62 ± 0.02	0.04135 ± 0.00008	4.259 ± 0.006	0.26 ± 0.01
5	initial	0	0	0	0.006 ± 0.003	4.75 ± 0.07	12.15 ± 0.08	0.0015 ± 0.0001	0.000	0.00
5	final	7650	1700	0.498 ± 0.003	1.714 ± 0.005	0.58 ± 0.03	5.51 ± 0.04	0.1341 ± 0.0001	7.27 ± 0.02	0.40 ± 0.01
6	initial	0	0	0	0	1.10 ± 0.21	0.988 ± 0.004	0.00024 ± 0.00003	0.000	0.00
6	final	7650	1700	0.009 ± 0.002	0.872 ± 0.003	0.000 ± 0.002	0.093 ± 0.002	0.00276 ± 0.00005	0.1763 ± 0.0004	0.03 ± 0.01
7	initial	0	0	0	0.0023 ± 0.0009	0.579 ± 0.009	1.282 ± 0.006	0.00023 ± 0.00003	0.000 ± 0.003	0.01 ± 0.01
7	final	7650	1700	0	0.834 ± 0.003	0.000 ± 0.009	0.406 ± 0.003	0.02375 ± 0.00008	1.090 ± 0.001	0.06 ± 0.01
8	initial	0	0	0	0.007 ± 0.002	1.43 ± 0.03	5.82 ± 0.02	0.00045 ± 0.00004	0.000	0.00
8	final	7650	1700	0	0.420 ± 0.002	0.00 ± 0.03	2.68 ± 0.02	0.38104 ± 0.00034	3.017 ± 0.003	0.20 ± 0.01
9	initial	0	0	0.001 ± 0.001	0.001 ± 0.001	1.95 ± 0.05	10.79 ± 0.05	0.00190 ± 0.00005	0.000 ± 0.000	0.002 ± 0.005
9	final	7650	1700	0	0.359 ± 0.003	0.00 ± 0.03	5.92 ± 0.04	0.56252 ± 0.00049	3.403 ± 0.004	0.39 ± 0.02
10	initial	0	0	0	0.002 ± 0.001	0.625 ± 0.002	0.090 ± 0.002	0.00015 ± 0.00002	0.000	0.001 ± 0.005
10	final	540	120	0.010 ± 0.002	0.148 ± 0.003	0.475 ± 0.002	0.082 ± 0.002	0.00049 ± 0.00004	0.0089 ± 0.0004	0.000
11	initial	0	0	0	0.000	0.833 ± 0.002	0.134 ± 0.002	0.00015 ± 0.00002	0.0000	0.000
11	final	540	120	0.014 ± 0.002	0.152 ± 0.002	0.686 ± 0.002	0.122 ± 0.002	0.00033 ± 0.00003	0.0113 ± 0.0004	0.002 ± 0.005
12	initial	0	0	0	0.000	1.585 ± 0.002	0.143 ± 0.002	0.00016 ± 0.00002	0.0000 ± 0.0002	0.006 ± 0.009
12	final	540	120	0.057 ± 0.002	0.143 ± 0.002	1.399 ± 0.002	0.130 ± 0.002	0.00046 ± 0.00004	0.0145 ± 0.0004	0.001 ± 0.006
13	initial	0	0	0	0.000	2.715 ± 0.002	0.135 ± 0.002	0.00017 ± 0.00002	0.0001 ± 0.0001	0.000
13	final	540	120	0.093 ± 0.001	0.170 ± 0.002	2.456 ± 0.002	0.128 ± 0.002	0.00030 ± 0.00003	0.0131 ± 0.0004	0.011 ± 0.008
14	initial	0	0	0	0.000	4.124 ± 0.003	0.179 ± 0.002	0.00020 ± 0.00003	0.0000 ±	0.001 ± 0.005
14	final	540	120	0.157 ± 0.002	0.234 ± 0.002	3.704 ± 0.002	0.164 ± 0.002	0.00030 0.00003±	0.0179 ± 0.0004	0.005 ± 0.006
15	initial	0	0	0.001 ± 0.002	0.000	8.566 ± 0.004	0.159 ± 0.002	0.00019 ± 0.00003	0.0001 ± 0.0001	0.000
15	final	540	120	0.312 ± 0.002	0.391 ± 0.002	8.534 ± 0.005	0.145 ± 0.002	0.00029 ± 0.00004	0.0337 ± 0.0004	0.000
16	initial	0	0	0	0.002 ± 0.001	15.883 ± 0.008	0.184 ± 0.002	0.00018 ± 0.00004	0.0000	0.000
16	final	540	120	0.428 ± 0.002	0.412 ± 0.002	15.544 ± 0.008	0.168 ± 0.002	0.00031 ± 0.00004	0.0549 ± 0.0004	0.01 ± 0.01

4 Degree of conversion of benzene

Figure S9: The amount of reacted benzene at 1700 s versus the initial amount of benzene. The slope of the linear regression is the degree of conversion

Here we define the degree of conversion as:

$$\xi_{1700\text{s}} = \frac{p_{\text{benzene}, 0\text{s}} - p_{\text{benzene}, 1700\text{s}}}{p_{\text{benzene}, 0\text{s}}}$$

The degree of conversion, shown in Figure S9 as the slope of the linear regression is 0.78 and even though the amount of water in the experiments is different. This shows that the decomposition of benzene does not depend on the initial amount of water.

5 Note on the reaction kinetics

A supporting argument for the fact that the decomposition rate of benzene does not depend on the amount of water can be made by plotting the initial rate of the reaction:

$$v_{\text{initial}} = \frac{k_1 p_{\text{C}_6\text{H}_6, 0\text{s}}}{k_2 + p_{\text{C}_6\text{H}_6, 0\text{s}}}$$

versus the relative amount of water to benzene at the beginning of the experiment (Figure S10). The figure shows that there is no clear correlation between the amount of water at the beginning and the benzene decomposition rate.

Figure S10: The initial benzene decomposition rate versus the relative amount of water at the beginning of the experiment. No clear trend can be deduced and therefore, the benzene decomposition rate does not depend on the amount of water.

6 Temporal evolution of species by experiment

Below, we show nine plots with the pressure of all the species monitored by infrared spectroscopy. The plots show the pressure changes in time as the irradiation goes. At the beginning, there is only benzene and water. As the experiment progresses, benzene and water are depleted and at the same time, HCN, C₂H₂, CH₄, CO and CO₂ emerge as the products.

Figure S11: The pressure of the monitored components in time in experiment no. 1 as denoted in Table 1 in the main text.

Figure S12: The pressure of the monitored components in time in experiment no. 2 as denoted in Table 1 in the main text.

Experiment 3

Figure S13: The pressure of the monitored components in time in experiment no. 3 as denoted in Table 1 in the main text.

Figure S14: The pressure of the monitored components in time in experiment no. 4 as denoted in Table 1 in the main text.

Experiment 5

Figure S15: The pressure of the monitored components in time in experiment no. 5 as denoted in Table 1 in the main text.

Experiment 6

Figure S16: The pressure of the monitored components in time in experiment no. 6 as denoted in Table 1 in the main text.

Experiment 7

Figure S17: The pressure of the monitored components in time in experiment no. 7 as denoted in Table 1 in the main text.

Experiment 8

Figure S18: The pressure of the monitored components in time in experiment no. 8 as denoted in Table 1 in the main text.

Figure S19: The pressure of the monitored components in time in experiment no. 9 as denoted in Table 1 in the main text.

7 Temporal evolution of species across experiments

The five plots below show the concentration in time for each species across different experiments. The plots show how in different experiments, various production rates of each species are observed.

Figure S20: The pressure of HCN in time in experiments no. 1-5 as denoted in Table 1 in the main text.

C_2H_2 - Experiments 1 - 5

Figure S21: The pressure of C_2H_2 in time in experiments no. 1-5 as denoted in Table 1 in the main text.

CH₄ - Experiments 1 - 5

Figure S22: The pressure of CH₄ in time in experiments no. 1-5 as denoted in Table 1 in the main text.

Figure S23: The pressure of CO in time in experiments no. 1-5 as denoted in Table 1 in the main text.

Figure S24: The pressure of CO₂ in time in experiments no. 1-5 as denoted in Table 1 in the main text.

Figure S25: The pressure of HCN in time in experiments no. 6-9 as denoted in Table 1 in the main text.

Figure S26: The pressure of C_2H_2 in time in experiments no. 6-9 as denoted in Table 1 in the main text.

Figure S27: The pressure of CH₄ in time in experiments no. 6-9 as denoted in Table 1 in the main text.

Figure S28: The pressure of CO in time in experiments no. 6-9 as denoted in Table 1 in the main text.

Figure S29: The pressure of CO₂ in time in experiments no. 6-9 as denoted in Table 1 in the main text.

8 Notes on the experiment

During the experiment, the mixture was constantly mixed with a fan. The fan flow is 3 mL s^{-1} . The mixing was observed on an example mixture of HCN, N_2 and CO_2 . As shown in figure S30, it takes about 25 measurements to reach steady state in the system at this mixing flow. Therefore, prior to each irradiation, we mixed the system for the deduced time until steady state was reached.

Figure S30: The composition of a mixture of HCN, CO_2 and N_2 monitored in time after filling. 200 measurements correspond to roughly 60 min. The mixture was constantly mixed with a fan at 3 mL s^{-1} flow.

A further complication arises from the adsorption and desorption of water. In the case, where no water was initially present, the water content increases. This is likely caused by desorption from the walls and a minor leak from the ambient air. Even though the apparatus was evacuated for 3 days with a rotary vane pump at dynamic background pressure 1×10^{-2} Torr, after stopping the evacuation and filling the system with gas, up to ~ 0.5 Torr of water desorbed from the walls.

In the second case, where 4 Torr of water was initially present, the water pressure decreases with time. This is likely caused by adsorption on the walls of the apparatus. In this case, we see that equilibration takes up to 60 min (200 measurements).

HCN_stability_miniPALS2: 2022_03_08_HCN+H2O_1.51

Figure S31: The composition of a mixture of HCN, CO₂, H₂O and N₂ monitored in time after filling. 200 measurements correspond to roughly 60 min. The mixture was constantly mixed with a fan at 3 mL s⁻¹ flow.

9 The experimental procedure

The following schematics show the sample cell and the irradiation cycles in the experiment. The figures show the initial mixture, irradiation with slow mixing, then fast mixing, FTIR analysis and then another irradiation. Irradiation steps are implicitly shown in the figures showing benzene decomposition. Identical intervals were used for all samples. Each sample was thoroughly mixed before irradiation (30 s at high fan speed) and each measurement took ~2 min to complete. The mixture is stable in this period of time.

Figure S32: A schematic drawing of the measurement cell for gas phase experiments.

Figure S33: A schematic drawing of the whole irradiation process. Parts X.1-X.5 always show the process of irradiation, mixing and FTIR analysis. A detailed description of the experimental flow is shown in the text in this section.

The drawing in figure S33 shows the experimental procedure. Picture 1.1 is the sample in the irradiation cell before the experiment. The gas flow is 3 mL s⁻¹ (“low gas flow”). The gas is shown as cubes with blue color. Blue represents the original mixture, and the cube size represents a volume of gas affected in each laser shot. In 1.2, one laser pulse is fired. This causes a reaction in the volume on the one cell, which modifies the cell’s composition. The cell after the reaction is shown in red. Since the gas flows all the time, the cell moves to the right and a new cell is irradiated (1.3). This goes on for a set time (intervals in the irradiation, here). After that, the irradiation is stopped (1.4), all the gas is thoroughly mixed (shown as lavender pink – blend between blue and red) and then, a FTIR spectrum is measured (1.5). A new interval of irradiation then begins with the gas already slightly modified after the first interval (hence the lavender pink color). The same cycle ensues and at the end, the color in the scheme changes to magenta to show mixing between the lavender and red (a further modification of the mixture). A third cycle then shows that the system reacts again (eggplant purple as a mixture of magenta and red) and in cycle 4, the final color is black. This schematic shows the workflow during the experiment.

10 Optical system losses

Figure S34: The measured power of the laser radiation with and without the entry window of the system.

The power of the laser radiation was measured with a power meter with and without the sample cell entry window to determine the losses at the window. The laser power is modified

by the FL-Q-Switch delay on the Q-Switch of the laser. The black curve in Figure S34 shows the measured laser power without any window and the red curve shows the power of the laser after the entry window. Both datasets were fitted with a cubic curve (no physical basis). The losses at the window are about 20%.

11 Background treatment

A background spectrum was measured prior to each experiment. An example of such spectrum is shown in figure S35.

Figure S35: An example of a background spectrum measured prior to one of the experiments.

This spectrum, measured in the same wavenumber range as the experiment, shows two bands of residual water. No other signals are present. The water signals originate from residual water in the sample cell (as mentioned in the main text, the background pressure before experiments was ~ 0.01 Torr) and also from the spectrometer itself, which operates under vacuum (~ 0.02 Torr). All spectra were measured using the boxcar apodization function (hence the “negative” peaks). The conditions in the laboratory were tested to be stable (by measuring background spectra after the experiment for random samples), so in the analysis, we fitted the background spectrum (obtained the column density, pressure broadening and temperature coefficients) and these were fitted to the sample spectra, effectively subtracting the background water signals from the sample.

12 SEM analysis

A solid sample from an experiment with benzene and N₂ was collected for SEM analysis. The sample cuvette after the experiment was opened and washed with methanol. The collected sample was stored in a refrigerator. The effect of ageing and oxidation due to exposure to ambient air are possible but were not further investigated. The SEM measurement was performed on a Hitachi S4800 scanning electron microscope. Figure S36 – S39 show different zoom on the sample loaded on an Si grid. The accelerating voltage was 20 kV. The size of the individual particles was determined to be typically between 20 and 70 nm, but a statistical distribution was not calculated.

Figure S36: A SEM image of the solid residue from an experiment with benzene and N₂. The figure shows a 500x zoom on the sample.

Figure S37: A SEM image of the solid residue from an experiment with benzene and N₂. The figure shows a 30 000x zoom on the sample.

Figure S38: A SEM image of the solid residue from an experiment with benzene and N₂. The figure shows a 50 000x zoom on the sample.

Figure S36: A SEM image of the solid residue from an experiment with benzene and N₂. The figure shows a 100 000x zoom on the sample.